

CREATIVE APPROACHES TO DEVELOP PUPILS' HIGH ORDER THINKING SKILLS

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Abstract

To the opportunities created, in the same time the industry revolution 4.0 is in fear of posing many threats to the less competent people in dealing with it. A lot of aspects in our lives will be influenced by; job vacancies, business models, industrial structures, social interactions, and governance systems. The high order thinking skills (HOTS) stands as a capability needed to engage in the 4.0 industrial revolution. The government of Republic of Indonesia itself is trying to integrate the HOTS into the education curriculum and mass job training for its citizen. While the HOTS training must also adjust to the preparedness and psychological ability of the subjected people, this study aims to develop the capacity of HOTS on community components, especially the younger generation. The research method we use is participatory action research, in which the researcher is directly involved to carry out creative approaches, intended to enhance their high-order thinking skills, and can be helpful for themselves, the family and the nearest society, as the solution improve the human resources quality to face the opportunities and challenges to the industrial revolution 4.0.

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I. Introduction

It's almost two centuries since the first industrial revolution was announced by Arnold Toynbee in 1884 [1]. Start from that time, concept of industrial revolution is often defined as a period where technology has brought big changes in society [2]. Since the first time, industrial revolution is reached the third stage. Starting in 1784-1870, industrial revolution was started in Britain as phenomena where the human labor and animals power has replaced by steam machine, coal, and water as a new power of industry [2]. In the end of 19 th century, a new source of energy was found, it called electricity. From that times, these new energy was massively produced and became an icon of 2 nd industrial revolution that led by United States [3]. After the discoveries about new sources of energy in the 1st and 2nd industrial revolution, the 3 rd industrial revolution that started in 1969-today wasn't found the new sources of energy,

instead of a new electronic tolls and information and technology for automatic manufacture [2][4].

After the 3rd stage of industrial revolution was found, there's a new concept about "Industrial Revolution 4.0" in Germany, specifically in Hannover Fair 2011[4]. Industrial revolution 4.0 is a unique phenomena because the real event just not started yet and it still a concept [5]. Industrial revolution 4.0 or industry 4.0 is integration from Cyber Physical System (CPS) and Internet of Things and Services (IoT and IoS) in industrial processes [6]. Industry 4.0 is defined as an industrial era where all of the aspect can communicated in the real time whenever and wherever with the internet technology and CPS [4] Industry 4.0 is predicted will bring big opportunities such as flexibility and resources efficiencies [1].

Industry 4.0 could fulfill the customer needs as an individual, make an optimal decision, and create a new model of business [6]. Besides all of the opportunities, industry 4.0 also creates many obstacles to faces. Resistance for demographical changes and society, political imbalance, lack of resources, disaster risk, and demands of safe technologies for the nature are the obstacles for a country that applied industry 4.0[5]. There are a lot of gap between technologies in industrial world today with technologies that needed in industry 4.0 [7]. Generally, there are 5 obstacles in industry 4.0; knowledge, technologies, economy, social, and politic [8].

Creativity is one of the biggest key of human development. A big, strategic, and structured plan is needed to face many obstacles in industry 4.0. As part of the society, researcher try to make an effort for the society about what people needs to face the industry 4.0; one of the efforts is an elucidation about High Order Thinking Skills (HOTS). These methods applied by using creative approaches with attractive games. These creative approaches were applied in the children with age range 5 to 7 years. Researcher belief the children could enjoy this activity and could create any creativity in the next time. All of the activities in this method are created to make a trigger in children analysis and evaluation skills. Hopefully, creative approaches with attractive games could become appropriate methods to build High Order Thinking Skills on children to counter the industrial revolution 4.0.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Industrial Revolution 4.0

Abrupt and radical change from the Fourth Industrial Revolution will create unprecedentedly fast and broad development of new technologies, and the interaction between them, thus offer new ways to create and consume, will transform how we deliver and access public services, and will enable new ways to communicate and govern thus invent massive influence on jobs, business models, industrial structures, social interactions, systems of governance. The transformative impact of this industry revolution 4.0 will demand that countries to adapt and think deeply about their policies and priorities [9].

The 4th Industrial Revolution, will influence the appropriate human resources for supporting the national development, one of the key to create qualified human resource to face this is through methods that increase the high order thinking skills in our education curriculum [10]. Automation and robots brought by the Industry Revolution 4.0 expected effect on the job availability. Given that these robots will be capable of performing tasks multiple times with high levels of accuracy and within shorter time duration than humans, robots will act as an efficient replacement for labor. Advanced technologies that reduce the need for workers helped companies in reducing lead time for prototype development. As a result, companies are able to speed-up their time to market, yet quantum of job loss will appear [11].

2.2 High Order Thinking Skills

With the environment change occurs in the Fourth Industrial, the skill required will also change. These new skill sets include creativity, logical reasoning, problem sensitivity, mathematical reasoning, visualization and capability to coordinating with others will ease adaptation to the changes that technological advancement brings [11] Thus the education curriculum which is include critical and creative thinking, reasoning and collaboration is required to produce creative and innovative students to face the Fourth Industrial Revolution. High Order Thinking is conceived as a capability to relate their learning to other elements beyond what is taught [12]. It is developed concept derives from Bloom's taxonomy, "top end": analyze, evaluate, create [13]. HOTS challenges us to interpret, analyze or manipulate information, with high level thinking, an individual will be able to use the new information or prior knowledge and manipulate information to obtain a reasonable response to new situations [14]. The high order thinking skills includes the capacity of critical thinking, creative thinking, communication and collaboration [10].

Dede stating that HOTS as structured inquiry are acquired when [15]:

1. learners construct knowledge rather than passively ingest information;
2. learners use sophisticated information gathering tools to be stimulated to focus on hypotheses rather than plotting data;
3. learners involve in collaborative interact with peers;
4. learners are measured for HOTS which is complex rather than simple recall of facts.

3. Objectives

Generally, aim of this research is for increase High Order Thinking Skills on children. It considered to makes a preparation on children to face the industry 4.0. The values of High Order Thinking Skills that adopted in this research are creativity, reasoning skills, and critical thinking ability. With the creative approaches and attractive games, the children could get more understanding about the materials that they learn.

In this research, High Order Thinking Skills was applied in the children with age range 5 to 7 years in a kindergarten in Rawamangun. The implementation was separated in three stages

that started with 1) Material Explanation, 2) Application of Ideas, 3) Describing Their Works. Beside of increasing the High Order Thinking Skills on children, this research also aiming for increasing the High Order Thinking Skills of the researcher as a college students.

The specific objectives of this study are to:

1. Socialize how important it is to be a creative individual.
2. Creating methods to enhance creative thinking of the pupils.
3. Familiarize learning approach that practicing High Order Thinking Skills among pupils by expectation to be habituated in daily life.

4. Methodology

In this study, a Participatory Action Research (PAR) in which both the researcher and the subject take an active to carry out creative approaches in fun and attractive games in order to enhance their high-level thinking skills. This activity was held in one day. About 15 girls and boys of 5-7 years old are involved. The games conducted have three main points;

1. Creativity
2. Reasoning Skills
3. Critical Thinking Ability

5. Implementation

The games conducted in group teamwork consist of 2 major teams, yet every child creates their own handcraft, every team was handled by one of researchers. This methods were conducted in three phase;

1. Material explanation, at this stage all children were explained about the material in integrated with their education curriculum agenda on that day. It aims to give clarification of what they should do. The material integrated on the day implementation conducted was about eating ethics.

2. Application of Ideas, at this stage children will be given an example of handcrafts based on the material taught, handcrafts in form of foods adapting the concept of slogan 4 healthy 5 perfect. After the handcraft examples were shown, children were asked to describe their ideas freely based on material that has been taught previously using origami paper media. This stage aims to improve creativity in children.

3. Describing their handcrafts, at this stage the children were asked about what they made using origami paper. This stage aims to form communication skills, reasoning, and critical thinking in children.

6. Results

Creativity, reasoning skills, and capacity to collaborate with others are some of the things that can be developed in children from an early age to face upcoming more advanced human society. In this study, researchers tried to integrate the concept of slogan “4 sehat 5 sempurna / 4 healthy 5 perfect” in learning where the researcher socialize about 4 healthy 5 perfect foods. In the beginning when the researcher shows the category of vegetables, children can understand it well, while when researchers try to ask children what is included in vegetables, children able mention one to two types of vegetables other than those shown by researchers. After the researchers explained about vegetables, the researchers explained various types of fruit. At this stage most children can mention the various types of fruit.

Besides vegetables and fruits, researchers tried to provide types of carbohydrate foods. When researchers explained carbohydrates foods, children did not seem to know much about carbohydrates other than those described by researchers, as well as protein. In addition to 4 healthy, researchers also explained about 5 perfect, which is milk. When the researchers explained the concept of 4 healthy 5 perfect, children were seen not knowing these categories of foods as well as vegetables and fruits.

On the third phase, the researcher continued with the second implementation phase, the application of ideas. At this stage the children will be given examples of handcraft based on the material taught, the form of food and drinks by the concept of 4 healthy 5 perfect. While the example of handcraft is shown, children were asked to make such handcrafts healthy by their own creativity. At this stage, several children seem a little confused to create the form, so that at this stage most children follow the form exemplified by researchers. Nevertheless, there are a small number of children who are able to make forms based on their creativity other than those exemplified by researchers. The handcrafts made by children based on the concept of 4 healthy 5 perfect, consists of fruits, vegetables, protein foods such as fish and sunny side up egg, and carbohydrate foods such as bread and corn. This second implementation phase by conducting the application of ideas aims to develop childrens creativity where children are able to describe what is in their minds into a form a handcraft made with origami paper. This is expected to be the trigger for children to habituate creative thinking and to keep innovating in the future.

The creation of the handcarfts is obviously has a meaning to the creator. After passing this second stage, children will enter the last stage, which is the stage of describing ideas. At this stage the children are asked to explain the reasons for the origami form they made. Some of the children answered that the food they made was the food they liked. Others answered that they were only able to form food that was easy to form. Through these three stages, it can be found that there are some children who have creativity and can create a different form than the example. In addition, children can give a reason for what they made when the researcher threw questions.

7. Discussion and Conclusion

Based on the result of the research. Creativity, reasoning skills, and critical thinking skills are three of the five aspects of High Order Thinking Skills that need to be possessed in the face of the Industrial Revolution 4.0. High Order Thinking Skills need to be developed early. Through this research, we can find that several children who were the subject of this study were able to applicate their creative thinking through handcrafts that were outside of the examples given. This shows that High Order Thinking Skills can be trained and given from very early using appropriate methods.

Besides being able to make a form of what is exemplified, children are also able to provide reasons for what they make. This shows that they are not only able to show their creativity, but also the ability to think critically and the ability to make a reason. If these abilities are trained continuously, this can certainly be an advantage for them to face all the challenges and obstacles that exist in the future. The ability to make an object using creativity and the ability to communicate what it makes is certainly a good thing especially for children.

Although there are children who have the excellent responses as explained above, there are also children who have not been able to demonstrate their creativity to the full. This is shown from the results of research that has been found that most of the children are less able to describe what is in their mind into an object that has a shape. Not only that, some children also cannot provide a reason that suits what they make. Even so, this does not at all indicate that child who cannot express what is on their minds as children who are not creative. Some factors can also be the background of these differences. For this reason, this study tries to initiate a method to improve this which consists of creativity, reasoning skills, and critical thinking skills.

Through this method, researchers think that a creative method to improve High Order Thinking Skills is necessary for the development of children, by a condition to give proper way to teach in accordance with the age and stages of the childs development. Researchers also hope that in the coming time this creative method can be a suggestion for parents, teachers, educational communities, and government institutions to provide support in implementing similar methods to improve the quality of education and human resources in order to create a better, innovative society.

8. Recommendation

Researchers are aware that the research that we are doing is still far from absolutely perfect, and still could be maximized, some things that can be done for further research that is better, is to conduct the methods in a more continuous long term to strengthen interventions in human behavior.

References

- [1] Lasi H, Fettke P, Kemper H G, Feld T & Hoffmann M. (2014). Industry 4.0. Business & Information Systems Engineering. 6 239.
- [2] Klingenberg C. (2017). Industry 4.0: What Makes a Revolutions?. Paper Presented in EurOMA 2017.
- [3] Freeman C, & Soete L. (1997). The economics of industrial innovation. Psychology Press.
- [4] Prasetyo H & Sutopo W. (2018). Industri 4.0: Telaah Klasifikasi Aspek dan Arah Pengembangan Riset. Jurnal Teknik Industri. 13 17.
- [5] Drath R, & Horch A. (2014). Industrie 4.0: Hit or hype? [industry forum]. IEEE industrial electronics magazine. 8 56.
- [6] Kagermann H, Lukas W D, & Wahlster W. (2013). Final report: Recommendations for implementing the strategic initiative INDUSTRIE 4.0. Industrie 4.0 Working Group.
- [7] Qin J, Liu Y, & Grosvenor R. (2016). A Categorical Framework of Manufacturing for Industry 4.0 and Beyond. Procedia CIRP. 52 173.
- [8] Zhou K, Taigang L, & Lifeng Z. (2015). Industry 4.0: Towards future industrial opportunities and challenges. In Fuzzy Systems and Knowledge Discovery (FSKD), IEEE 12th International Conference, 2147.
- [9] Wood J, et al. (2017). ASEAN 4.0: What does the Fourth Industrial Revolution mean for regional economic integration?. ADB & WEF.
- [10] Nasir M. (2018). Policy for Curriculum and Competencies in the 4th Industrial Revolution. The Ministry of Research Technology and Higher Education Republic of Indonesia
- [11] Aulbur W, et al. (2016). Skill Development for Indutry 4.0. Roland Berger.
- [12] Brookhart, Susan M. (2010). How to Assess Higher-Order Thinking Skills in Your Classroom. Virginia: ASCD
- [12] Krathwohl, D. R. (2002). A Revision of Bloom's Taxonomy. 41 212.
- [13] Heong, Y. M. et al. (2012). The needs analysis of learning higher order thinking skills for generating ideas. 59 197.
- [14] Dede C. Imagining Technology's Role in Restructuring for Learning. In K. Sheingold and M.S Tucker (Eds).

